

Apparent molar volumes of tartaric acid in water and in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K

Radha Rani Gupta and Mukhtar Singh*

Department of Chemistry, Agra College, Agra-282 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : mukhtarsingh2003@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 5 March 2009, revised 20 July 2009, accepted 21 July 2009

Abstract : Apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) have been determined for tartaric acid in water and in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides at different concentrations by measuring the densities at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K. The limiting apparent molar volume, V_ϕ^0 , (which is equal to the partial molar volume, V_2^0 at infinite dilution) and experimental slope (S_v) have been obtained in each case. The partial molar volumes (V_2^0) have been used to calculate the partial molar volumes of transfer (ΔV_ϕ^0) of tartaric acid from water to aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides at different temperatures. The values of limiting apparent molar expansibilities (Φ_E^0) and that of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_p$ have been determined from temperature-dependence of V_ϕ^0 . The values of pair and triplet coefficients have been determined from ΔV_ϕ^0 . It is concluded that tartaric acid behaves as structure maker in water as well as in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides.

Keywords : Apparent molar volumes, tartaric acid, aqueous solutions of saccharides.

Introduction

In previous publications^{1,2}, we have reported the results of our studies on the determination of densities and apparent molar volumes of oxalic acid (dihydrate) in water and in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides at different temperatures. Parmar *et al.*^{3,4} have reported studies on the determination of partial molar volumes of tartaric acid in water and in binary aqueous mixtures of ethanol and urea of varying molalities at different temperatures. A survey of literature shows that apparent molar volumes of tartaric acid in water and in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides at different temperatures vis-a-vis solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions are still lacking. Hence, the title study has been undertaken.

Results and discussion

The apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of L(+)-tartaric acid in water and in aqueous solutions of D(+)-glucose, D(-)-fructose, L-sorbose, sucrose and D(+)-maltose (monohydrate) (as solvents) of varying molality (m_s) have been determined as a function of molality (m) of the solutions of L(+)-tartaric acid, from the density data, at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K, using eq. (1).

$$V_\phi = \frac{1000 (\rho_0 - \rho)}{m \rho \rho_0} + \frac{M}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

where m is the molality of L(+)-tartaric acid solution, ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of the solution and the solvent, respectively. M is the molecular weight of the solute (L(+)-tartaric acid). The representative data in respect of densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of tartaric acid in aqueous solutions and in the presence of aqueous solutions of D(+)-glucose at different temperatures have been presented in Table 1.

The plots of V_ϕ versus m are linear in each case at different temperatures (representative Figs. 1 and 2). From this it follows that the variations of V_ϕ of L(+)-tartaric acid with m in water and also in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides can be represented by the following equation,

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v m \quad (2)$$

where V_ϕ^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume at infinite dilution (which is equal to the partial molar volume of the solute, V_2^0) and S_v is the experimental slope⁵ (sometimes^{6,7} considered to be the volumetric pairwise interactions coefficient). V_ϕ^0 is a measure of solute-solvent in-

*Address for correspondence : H.I.G. 142, Shastri Puram, Sikandra, Agra-282 007, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Table 1. Densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of L(+)-tartaric acid as a function of molality (m) in water and in aqueous solutions of D(+)-glucose at different temperatures

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	293.15 K		303.15 K		313.15 K		323.15 K	
	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)
D(+)-Glucose								
$m_s = 0.0 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$								
0.0000	0.99823	-	0.99568	-	0.99224	-	0.98807	-
0.4144	1.02530	82.56	1.02248	83.46	1.01879	84.37	1.01442	85.23
0.6325	1.03871	82.77	1.03578	83.62	1.03197	84.53	1.02750	85.39
0.8584	1.05200	83.03	1.04899	83.82	1.04507	84.71	1.04052	85.55
1.0927	1.06522	83.25	1.06208	84.05	1.05812	84.87	1.05343	85.75
1.3360	1.07834	83.48	1.07504	84.32	1.07102	85.10	1.06627	85.95
1.5888	1.09131	83.75	1.08795	84.55	1.08380	85.35	1.07907	86.12
1.8516	1.10428	83.96	1.10076	84.78	1.09660	85.53	1.09175	86.32
2.1257	1.11695	84.28	1.11341	85.05	1.10914	85.81	1.10435	86.52
2.4120	1.12937	84.67	1.12600	85.30	1.12160	86.08	1.11688	86.72
$m_s = 0.5307 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$								
0.0000	1.03223	-	1.02932	-	1.02574	-	1.02136	-
0.4008	1.05812	82.71	1.05493	83.62	1.05101	84.73	1.04633	85.83
0.6117	1.07090	82.96	1.06764	83.78	1.06355	84.89	1.05864	86.10
0.8303	1.08363	83.16	1.08024	83.98	1.07605	85.02	1.07095	86.26
1.0569	1.09623	83.40	1.09275	84.20	1.08840	85.24	1.08318	86.42
1.2922	1.10872	83.65	1.10518	84.40	1.10062	85.49	1.09530	86.62
1.5368	1.12110	83.91	1.11738	84.71	1.11291	85.62	1.10740	86.78
1.7914	1.13331	84.20	1.12963	84.91	1.12489	85.91	1.11929	87.02
2.0566	1.14541	84.49	1.14183	85.09	1.13692	86.11	1.13113	87.24
2.3331	1.15743	84.76	1.15380	85.35	1.14894	86.27	1.14296	87.42
$m_s = 1.1294 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$								
0.0000	1.06559	-	1.06240	-	1.05865	-	1.05408	-
0.3883	1.09030	82.88	1.08678	83.92	1.08261	85.19	1.07778	86.17
0.5926	1.10248	83.15	1.09886	84.08	1.09452	85.31	1.08951	86.37
0.8044	1.11458	83.38	1.11082	84.31	1.10632	85.49	1.10117	86.54
1.0240	1.12664	83.56	1.12262	84.59	1.11799	85.72	1.11279	86.69
1.2521	1.13847	83.86	1.13441	84.79	1.12964	85.89	1.12430	86.87
1.4891	1.15031	84.07	1.14609	85.01	1.14118	86.09	1.13579	87.02
1.7358	1.16190	84.36	1.15770	85.21	1.15258	86.32	1.14702	87.28
1.9928	1.17343	84.63	1.16895	85.56	1.16379	86.60	1.15822	87.50
2.2608	1.18481	84.91	1.18025	85.81	1.17507	86.79	1.16937	87.70
$m_s = 1.8102 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$								
0.0000	1.09886	-	1.09475	-	1.09060	-	1.08625	-
0.3766	1.12212	83.67	1.11761	84.88	1.11312	86.00	1.10836	87.29
0.5750	1.13360	83.90	1.12884	85.20	1.12425	86.20	1.11923	87.56
0.7806	1.14486	84.26	1.13994	85.50	1.13516	86.55	1.13006	87.76
0.9941	1.15602	84.57	1.15098	85.73	1.14588	86.94	1.14078	87.97
1.2160	1.16698	84.93	1.16171	86.13	1.15668	87.13	1.15134	88.24
1.4467	1.17782	85.26	1.17227	86.52	1.16728	87.40	1.16177	88.51

Table-1 (contd.)

1.6870	1.18857	85.56	1.18294	86.75	1.17770	87.71	1.17221	88.71
1.9383	1.19882	86.05	1.19319	87.14	1.18782	88.10	1.18216	89.12
2.2005	1.20907	86.44	1.20328	87.53	1.19779	88.48	1.19238	89.32
$m_s = 2.5932 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$								
0.0000	1.13156	-	1.12694	-	1.12254	-	1.11795	-
0.3658	1.15349	84.18	1.14859	85.16	1.14385	86.23	1.13877	87.69
0.5586	1.16423	84.52	1.15917	85.53	1.15432	86.51	1.14903	87.92
0.7585	1.17479	84.88	1.16960	85.87	1.16469	86.76	1.15922	88.11
0.9660	1.18525	85.19	1.17998	86.12	1.17494	87.02	1.16928	88.34
1.1818	1.19553	85.53	1.19006	86.51	1.18501	87.33	1.17910	88.67
1.4064	1.20557	85.92	1.20014	86.79	1.19495	87.63	1.18893	88.90
1.6406	1.21539	86.34	1.21009	87.07	1.20473	87.94	1.19857	89.18
1.8850	1.22505	86.74	1.21957	87.52	1.21432	88.28	1.20809	89.46
2.1405	1.23455	87.13	1.22896	87.92	1.22396	88.53	1.21754	89.71

m_s = Molality of solvent [aqueous solutions of D(+)-glucose].

Fig. 1. Plots of apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) versus m for L(+)-tartaric acid in purely aqueous medium at different temperatures : (o) 293.15; (■) 303.15; (▲) 313.15 and (◦) 323.15 K.

Fig. 2. Plots of apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) versus m for L(+)-tartaric acid in aqueous solutions of D(+)-glucose (0.53 m) at different temperatures : (o) 293.15; (■) 303.15; (▲) 313.15 and (◦) 323.15 K.

teractions⁸ while S_v is a measure of solute-solute interactions⁹. The values of V_ϕ^0 and S_v have been obtained at different temperatures by least squares fitting of $V_\phi - m$ data to eq. (2). The results are presented in Table 2 along with the standard errors (in the parentheses) with regard to the values of V_ϕ^0 and S_v . The standard deviation (S.D.) of the fit is also mentioned in this table. It is found that the fit of $V_\phi - m$ data to eq. (2) is excellent.

In literature, the theoretical value of V_ϕ^0 for L(+)-

tartaric acid obtained from additivity principle¹⁰ is reported as $86.0 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (or $86.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) at 298.15 K. This compares fairly well, keeping in view the mode of variation of V_ϕ^0 with temperature¹⁰, with the corresponding experimental value of $83.04 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (or $83.04 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) obtained in purely aqueous solutions at 303.15 K in the present study. Thus the experimental values of V_ϕ^0 of L(+)-tartaric acid at different temperatures (vide Table 2) are compatible with the theo-

Table 2. Limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slope (S_{ν}) of L(+)-tartaric acid in water an in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides of varying molality at different temperatures

Molality (m_s) (mol kg ⁻¹) of mono- and disaccharides	$10^6 \cdot V_{\phi}^0$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)				$10^6 \cdot S_{\nu}$ (m ³ kg mol ⁻¹)				S.D. ^a			
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K
D(+)-Glucose												
0.0 (water)	82.12 (±0.04)	83.04 (±0.02)	83.98 (±0.04)	84.92 (±0.02)	1.03 (±0.04)	0.94 (±0.02)	0.85 (±0.03)	0.74 (±0.01)	0.0008	0.0007	0.0015	0.0011
0.5307	82.29 (±0.01)	83.24 (±0.04)	84.38 (±0.05)	85.57 (±0.04)	1.06 (±0.01)	0.91 (±0.03)	0.82 (±0.04)	0.79 (±0.03)	0.0004	0.0004	0.0008	0.0008
1.1294	82.49 (±0.02)	83.51 (±0.03)	84.81 (±0.03)	85.87 (±0.03)	1.07 (±0.02)	1.01 (±0.03)	0.87 (±0.03)	0.79 (±0.03)	0.0008	0.0005	0.0012	0.0018
1.8102	83.06 (±0.02)	84.36 (±0.03)	85.49 (±0.04)	86.89 (±0.04)	1.53 (±0.04)	1.43 (±0.04)	1.33 (±0.06)	1.09 (±0.04)	0.0007	0.0004	0.0003	0.0012
2.5932	83.59 (±0.01)	84.67 (±0.03)	85.77 (±0.02)	87.26 (±0.03)	1.66 (±0.02)	1.50 (±0.05)	1.30 (±0.03)	1.14 (±0.03)	0.0003	0.0008	0.0001	0.0008
D(-)-Fructose												
0.5306	82.70 (±0.02)	83.71 (±0.04)	84.68 (±0.02)	85.80 (±0.03)	0.99 (±0.02)	0.90 (±0.04)	0.87 (±0.02)	0.86 (±0.03)	0.0013	0.0014	0.0007	0.0007
1.1298	84.07 (±0.02)	85.11 (±0.01)	86.12 (±0.03)	87.22 (±0.04)	1.18 (±0.03)	1.15 (±0.02)	1.09 (±0.03)	0.88 (±0.03)	0.0012	0.0013	0.0012	0.0009
1.8106	84.64 (±0.03)	85.71 (±0.04)	86.92 (±0.02)	88.09 (±0.03)	1.37 (±0.04)	1.28 (±0.06)	1.10 (±0.03)	1.06 (±0.03)	0.0004	0.0016	0.0013	0.0015
2.5926	85.75 (±0.04)	86.92 (±0.03)	88.08 (±0.02)	89.27 (±0.02)	1.60 (±0.06)	1.51 (±0.04)	1.42 (±0.03)	1.25 (±0.02)	0.0015	0.0006	0.0005	0.0081
L-Sorbose												
0.5300	82.26 (±0.02)	83.23 (±0.03)	84.20 (±0.04)	85.21 (±0.05)	1.03 (±0.02)	0.90 (±0.03)	0.85 (±0.03)	0.80 (±0.04)	0.0006	0.0013	0.0002	0.0015
1.1272	82.63 (±0.02)	83.62 (±0.04)	84.73 (±0.02)	85.75 (±0.03)	1.12 (±0.03)	1.01 (±0.04)	0.97 (±0.02)	0.88 (±0.03)	0.0013	0.0011	0.0009	0.0001
1.8052	84.39 (±0.04)	85.42 (±0.02)	86.43 (±0.04)	87.54 (±0.04)	1.17 (±0.04)	1.16 (±0.03)	1.02 (±0.05)	0.92 (±0.04)	0.0012	0.0009	0.0006	0.0003
2.5809	87.86 (±0.02)	88.88 (±0.04)	89.90 (±0.03)	91.00 (±0.04)	1.19 (±0.02)	1.17 (±0.05)	1.10 (±0.03)	0.99 (±0.04)	0.0011	0.0007	0.0015	0.0001
Sucrose												
0.5614	82.70 (±0.02)	83.71 (±0.03)	84.76 (±0.04)	86.00 (±0.04)	0.86 (±0.02)	0.83 (±0.03)	0.82 (±0.03)	0.72 (±0.03)	0.0011	0.0016	0.0009	0.0013
1.2821	83.08 (±0.03)	84.20 (±0.04)	85.74 (±0.06)	86.98 (±0.03)	1.15 (±0.04)	1.08 (±0.04)	0.91 (±0.05)	0.86 (±0.03)	0.0007	0.0001	0.0005	0.0018
2.2411	84.28 (±0.01)	85.36 (±0.03)	86.40 (±0.05)	87.53 (±0.03)	1.15 (±0.02)	1.10 (±0.04)	1.00 (±0.05)	0.89 (±0.02)	0.0010	0.0016	0.0015	0.0001
3.5800	85.83 (±0.05)	86.84 (±0.06)	88.36 (±0.04)	89.39 (±0.07)	1.26 (±0.06)	1.19 (±0.07)	1.14 (±0.05)	1.04 (±0.07)	0.0015	0.0017	0.0017	0.0011
D(+)-Maltose (monohydrate)												
0.1025	82.29 (±0.02)	83.39 (±0.03)	84.44 (±0.04)	85.60 (±0.08)	1.01 (±0.02)	0.88 (±0.03)	0.78 (±0.03)	0.50 (±0.04)	0.0008	0.0008	0.0018	0.0005

Table-2 (contd.)

0.5657	82.97 (±0.02)	84.00 (±0.04)	85.21 (±0.05)	86.29 (±0.05)	1.06 (±0.02)	0.89 (±0.04)	0.80 (±0.04)	0.58 (±0.03)	0.0016	0.0001	0.0013	0.0008
1.3020	84.45 (±0.02)	85.51 (±0.04)	86.87 (±0.04)	88.06 (±0.04)	1.19 (±0.02)	1.03 (±0.04)	0.94 (±0.04)	0.71 (±0.02)	0.0007	0.0016	0.0011	0.0010

Standard errors are given in parentheses.

^aStandard deviation of the fit of eq. (2), $V_{\phi} = V_{\phi}^0 + S_v m$.

retical values. On the other hand, the experimental value of V_{ϕ}^0 for tartaric acid in aqueous medium reported by Parmar *et al.*^{3,4} is $41.0 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 298.15 K, which is absurd.

From Table 2 it is also seen that the values of V_{ϕ}^0 for L(+)-tartaric acid, in water as well as in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides are largely positive at different temperatures thereby suggesting the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions in solutions of L(+)-tartaric acid in these solvent systems. On the other hand, the values of S_v for L(+)-tartaric acid are very small in comparison with those of V_{ϕ}^0 . From this it follows that the strength of solute-solute interactions is much smaller as compared to that of solute-solvent interactions.

Partial molar volumes of transfer, ΔV_{ϕ}^0 , of L(+)-tartaric acid from water to aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides (as solvents) have been obtained from the following relation,

$$\Delta V_{\phi}^0 = [V_{\phi}^0 \text{ (in aq. solutions of D(+)-glucose/ D(-)-fructose/L-sorbose/sucrose/D(+)-maltose (monohydrate))} - V_{\phi}^0 \text{ (in water)}] \quad (3)$$

It is seen that the values of ΔV_{ϕ}^0 are positive for the L(+)-tartaric acid and increase with increasing concentration (m_s) of mono- and disaccharides. In other words, there occurs an increase in the volume in going from water to aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides.

The transfer volumes (ΔV_{ϕ}^0) of L(+)-tartaric acid can also be expressed by the McMillan-Mayer theory¹¹ of solutions. Kozak *et al.*¹² have proposed a formalism based on the McMillan-Mayer theory which permits the formal separation of the effects due to interactions between pairs of solute molecules and those due to interactions between three or more solute molecules. This approach has further been discussed by Friedmann and Krishnan¹³ and Frank *et al.*¹⁴ in order to include the solute-cosolute interactions in the solvation spheres. According to this treatment, a thermodynamic transfer function at infinite dilution, ΔV_{ϕ}^0 , can be expressed as,

$$\Delta V_{\phi}^0 = 2V_{AB} m_B + 3V_{ABB} m_B^2 + \dots \quad (4)$$

where A stands for L(+)-tartaric acid, B stands for D(+)-glucose/D(-)-fructose/L-sorbose/sucrose/D(+)-maltose (monohydrate) and m_B is the molality of cosolute [D(+)-glucose/D(-)-fructose/L-sorbose/sucrose/(+)-maltose (monohydrate)], V_{AB} and V_{ABB} are the pair and triplet intermolecular interaction coefficients. The ΔV_{ϕ}^0 data have been fitted to the above eq. (4) to obtain V_{AB} and V_{ABB} interaction coefficients which are given in Table 3. It is seen that the values of V_{AB} for L(+)-tartaric acid are

Table 3. Values of pair (V_{AB}) and triplet (V_{ABB}) interaction coefficients for L(+)-tartaric acid in aqueous solutions of mono-[D(+)-glucose, D(-)-fructose and L-sorbose] and disaccharides [sucrose and D(+)-maltose (monohydrate)] at different temperatures

Temp. (K)	$10^6 \cdot V_{AB}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ kg}$) D(+)-Glucose	$10^6 \cdot V_{ABB}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-3} \text{ kg}^2$)
293.15	0.1200	0.0430
303.15	0.2321	0.0251
313.15	0.4429	-0.0228
323.15	0.5554	-0.0240
	D(-)-Fructose	
293.15	0.7909	-0.0242
303.15	0.8501	-0.0276
313.15	0.9100	-0.0307
323.15	1.0226	-0.0478
	L-Sorbose	
293.15	-0.3945	0.3867
303.15	-0.3461	0.3794
313.15	-0.2683	0.3627
323.15	-0.2113	0.3560
	Sucrose	
293.15	0.3766	0.0265
303.15	0.4726	0.0109
313.15	0.6013	-0.0001
323.15	0.7627	-0.0288
	D(+)-Maltose (monohydrate)	
293.15	0.6507	0.1245
303.15	0.8555	0.0452
313.15	1.1819	-0.0394
323.15	1.3975	-0.1019

positive in the presence of D(+)-glucose, D(-)-fructose, sucrose and D(+)-maltose (monohydrate) at different temperatures but are negative in the presence of L-sorbose. On the other hand, the values of V_{ABB} are positive in the presence of L-sorbose, but the values are negative in the presence of D(-)-fructose. As for sucrose, D(+)-glucose and D(+)-maltose (monohydrate) the values of V_{ABB} are negative at higher temperatures (313.15 and 323.15 K). However, the values are positive at lower temperatures (293.15 and 303.15 K).

The values of ϕ_E^0 and the derivative $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_p$ for L(+)-tartaric acid have been obtained from the temperature dependence of V_ϕ^0 which is given by following equation^{15,16},

$$V_\phi^0 = a_0 + a_1T + a_2T^2 \quad (5)$$

The values of coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 have been calculated by least squares fitting of the V_ϕ^0 - temperature (T) data into eq. (5) and are listed in Table 4.

Table 4. Values of coefficients, a_0 , a_1 and a_2 for aqueous solutions of L(+)-tartaric acid in water and in presence of mono- and disaccharides (as solvents) of varying molality (m_s)

m_s (mol kg ⁻¹)	$10^6 \cdot a_0$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$10^6 \cdot a_1$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	$10^6 \cdot a_2$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻²)
D(+)-Glucose			
0.0 (water)	60.9	0.053	0.0001
0.5307	105.2	-0.249	0.0006
1.1294	59.6	0.045	0.0001
1.8102	69.0	-0.023	0.0002
2.5932	145.9	-0.515	0.0010
D(-)-Fructose			
0.5306	77.7	-0.061	0.0003
1.1298	66.4	0.020	0.0001
1.8106	75.2	-0.043	0.0003
2.5926	56.8	0.082	0.0001
L-Sorbose			
0.5300	64.4	0.027	0.0001
1.1272	57.6	0.068	0.0001
1.8052	73.4	-0.023	0.0002
2.5809	75.5	-0.014	0.0002
Sucrose			
0.5614	106.1	-0.251	0.0006
1.2821	71.2	-0.043	0.0003
2.2411	64.9	0.028	0.0001
3.5800	53.1	0.102	0.00003
D(+)-Maltose (monohydrate)			
0.1025	66.0	0.007	0.0002
0.5657	60.4	0.045	0.0001
1.3020	82.1	-0.095	0.0004

The limiting apparent molar expansibilities, ϕ_E^0 of L(+)-tartaric acid have been calculated¹⁵ from the following equation,

$$\phi_E^0 = (\partial V_\phi^0 / \partial T)_p = a_1 + 2a_2T \quad (6)$$

The values of ϕ_E^0 at different temperatures are listed in Table 5. It is seen that the values of ϕ_E^0 for L(+)-tartaric acid are positive in purely aqueous medium as well as in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides and increase with the rise in temperature. From this it follows¹⁷ that L(+)-tartaric acid behaves as a structure maker in purely aqueous medium as well as in solutions of mono- and disaccharides.

Hepler¹⁸ has proposed a method by which qualitative information on hydration of solutes can be obtained from thermal expansion of aqueous solution by the following

Table 5. Limiting apparent molar expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) for L(+)-tartaric acid in water and in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides of varying molality (m_s) at different temperatures

m_s (mol kg ⁻¹)	$10^6 \cdot \phi_E^0$ (m ⁶ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)			
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K
D(+)-Glucose				
0.0 (water)	0.0914	0.0927	0.0940	0.0953
0.5307	0.0925	0.1041	0.1158	0.1274
1.1294	0.1110	0.1132	0.1155	0.1177
1.8102	0.1190	0.1238	0.1287	0.1335
2.5932	0.0903	0.1110	0.1316	0.1523
D(-)-Fructose				
0.5306	0.0947	0.1000	0.1054	0.1107
1.1298	0.1005	0.1033	0.1060	0.1088
1.8106	0.1077	0.1129	0.1180	0.1232
2.5926	0.1155	0.1166	0.1178	0.1189
L-Sorbose				
0.5300	0.0947	0.0970	0.0993	0.1016
1.1272	0.1029	0.1041	0.1053	0.1065
1.8052	0.0984	0.1025	0.1067	0.1108
2.5809	0.0985	0.1023	0.1062	0.1100
Sucrose				
0.5614	0.0918	0.1035	0.1152	0.1269
1.2821	0.1239	0.1296	0.1353	0.1410
2.2411	0.1042	0.1068	0.1094	0.1120
3.5800	0.1209	0.1216	0.1222	0.1229
D(+)-Maltose (monohydrate)				
0.1025	0.1048	0.1082	0.1115	0.1149
0.5657	0.1085	0.1106	0.1128	0.1149
1.3020	0.1114	0.1184	0.1255	0.1325

relation,

$$(\partial C_P^0/\partial P)_T = -T(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P \quad (7)$$

According to this, the left hand side of the above equation should be positive for all structure breaking solutes and therefore, structure breaking solutes possess negative value of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P$. On the other hand, positive value of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P$ should be associated with structure making solutes.

The values of the derivative, $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P$ in respect of L(+)-tartaric acid are presented in Table 6. These are positive in purely aqueous medium and also in aqueous solutions of D(+)-glucose/D(-)-fructose/L-sorbose/sucrose/D(+)-maltose (monohydrate). These positive values support the structure making tendency of L(+)-tartaric acid in purely aqueous medium and also in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides. The conclusions relating to

the effect of temperature on the values of V_ϕ^0 and ϕ_E^0 are in agreement with those reported in the recent literature¹⁹⁻²¹.

Experimental

CHOHCOOH
L(+)-Tartaric acid, | (Mol. wt. 150) was
CHOHCOOH

Merck product of analytical reagent grade and was used as such. The monosaccharides used in this study included D(+)-glucose (Mol. wt. 180), D(-)-fructose (Mol. wt. 180) and L-sorbose (Mol. wt. 180). These were Merck products of analytical reagent grade of 99.9% purity. The disaccharides, sucrose (Mol. wt. 342) and D(+)-maltose (monohydrate) (Mol. wt. 360) were also Merck products of 99.9% purity. These were dried over P₂O₅ in a vacuum desiccator. Standard stock solutions of tartaric acid and all saccharides were prepared using water having specific conductance less than 10⁻⁶ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹ which was degassed before use. Weighing was done on a Mettler balance having an accuracy of ±1 × 10⁻⁴ g. All the solutions were prepared afresh on a molality scale. The densities of solutions were measured by using digital vibrating tube densimeter (Model 60/602 Anton Parr, Austria). The temperature of the water flowing around the densimeter cell was controlled within ±0.01 K using an efficient temperature bath. The uncertainties of the density measurements were estimated to ±1 × 10⁻⁵ g cm⁻³.

References

1. R. R. Gupta and M. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 184.
2. R. R. Gupta and M. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2007, **46**, 455.
3. M. L. Parmar, R. K. Awasthi and M. K. Guleria, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2004, **116**, 33.
4. M. L. Parmar, O. P. Sharma and M. K. Guleria, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 1868.
5. G. R. Hedwig, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1988, **17**, 383.
6. J. E. Desnoyers, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1982, **54**, 1469.
7. G. R. Hedwig, J. F. Reading and T. H. Lilley, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1991, **87**, 1751.
8. K. Belibagli and E. Agranci, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1990, **19**, 867.
9. R. K. Wadi and P. Ramasami, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1997, **93**, 243.
10. H. Hoiland, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1974, **A28**, 699.
11. W. G. McMillan (Jr.) and J. E. Mayer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **13**, 276.

Table 6. Values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P$ for L(+)-tartaric acid in water and in presence of aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides of varying molality (m_s)		
m_s (mol kg ⁻¹)		$10^{12} \cdot (\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P$ (m ⁶ mol ⁻² K ⁻²)
	D(+)-Glucose	
0.0 (water)		0.0001
0.5307		0.0012
1.1294		0.0002
1.8102		0.0005
2.5932		0.0021
	D(-)-Fructose	
0.5306		0.0005
1.1298		0.0003
1.8106		0.0005
2.5926		0.0001
	L-Sorbose	
0.5300		0.0002
1.1272		0.0001
1.8052		0.0004
2.5809		0.0004
	Sucrose	
0.5614		0.0012
1.2821		0.0006
2.2411		0.0003
3.5800		0.0001
	D(+)-Maltose (monohydrate)	
0.1025		0.0003
0.5657		0.0002
1.3020		0.0007

12. J. J. Kozak, W. S. Knight and W. Kauzmann, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **48**, 675.
13. H. L. Friedman and C. V. Krishnan, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1973, **2**, 37.
14. F. Franks, M. Pedley and D. S. Reid, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1976, **72**, 359.
15. P. S. Nikam, A. S. Sawant, J. S. Aher and R. S. Khainer, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 197.
16. B. S. Lark, P. Patyar, T. S. Banipal and N. Kishore, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2004, **49**, 553.
17. A. Pal and S. Kumar, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2005, **117**, 267.
18. L. Hepler, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 4613.
19. R. Sadeghi and B. Goodazi, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2008, **53**, 26.
20. C. Klofutar, J. Horvat and D. R. Tasic, *Acta Chim. Slov.*, 2006, **53**, 274.
21. A. Ali, S. Khan and F. Nabi, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **72**, 495.